

Cellular structure of wreath product \vec{S}_n using signed Brauer diagrams

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Abstract: In this paper we prove that the wreath product $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ with symmetric group S_n , is cellular for algebra $Z_2(x)$. We obtain simple cell modules which satisfy semi-simplicity conditions. We make use of method of iterated inflations for this purpose.

Keywords: cellular algebra, signed Brauer algebras, symmetric groups, wreath product.

1. Introduction:

The wreath product $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is a semi-direct product of group algebras Z_2 and S_n whose elements are represented by using signed Brauer diagrams. A new class of algebras namely signed Brauer's algebras denoted by $\vec{B}_n(x)$ for a positive integer n and a complex number x was first introduced by Parvathi and Kamaraj [2]. $\vec{B}_n(x)$ contain the Brauer algebras $B_n(x)$ and the group algebras $C\vec{S}_n$ where $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is a wreath product of Z_2 by S_n . In a graph, if every edge is labelled by either a plus sign or a minus sign then it is called the signed diagram. These edges are called signed edges. An edge labelled by plus sign is called a *positive* edge, denoted by \downarrow (\rightarrow) and an edge labelled by negative sign is called a *negative* edge denoted by \uparrow (\leftarrow). $\vec{B}_n(x)$ is an associative algebra with a basis of signed diagrams and multiplication defined in it. Elements of \vec{S}_n are represented by the signed diagrams with no horizontal edges. Thus the structure of semi-simple algebras $C\vec{S}_n$ helps to understand the structure of signed Brauer algebra. \vec{S}_n is a wreath product of group algebras Z_2^n and S_n where $Z_2^n = \{f | f : \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \rightarrow Z_2\}$ is an associative unital algebra and S_n is a symmetric group of order n . For $n \geq 2$, \vec{S}_n becomes a subgroup of the symmetric group S_{2n} . Graham Leherer in [1] introduced the cellular algebra and since then it has its wide applications in many fields like the representation theory of wreath product algebra. R. Green [3, 4] has proved that for any cellular algebra A , the wreath product $A \wr S_n$ is cellular if it is an iterated inflation of tensor products of group algebras of symmetric groups. König and Xi [5, 6] were the first to introduce the concept of iterated inflation of tensor products and R. Green [4] has applied it for cellular algebras. Sharma R.P., Parmar R. and Kapil V.S. [7] have constructed a complete set of inequivalent irreducible \vec{S}_n -modules and used it to understand cellular structure of $\vec{B}_n(x)$. T. Geetha and F.M. Goodman [8] have proved that the wreath product algebras $A \wr G_n$ and A -Brauer algebras $D_n(A)$ both are cyclic cellular algebras if A is a cyclic cellular algebra. In this paper we prove that wreath product algebra $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ cyclic cellular algebra provided the group algebra $Z_2^n(x)$ with symmetric group S_n is a cyclic cellular algebra. We obtain the simple modules and cell modules which satisfy a semi-simplicity condition for \vec{S}_n . We make use the method of iterated inflations to achieve this.

2. Preliminaries: For a field R of characteristic p , let $Z_2^n(x)$ be an unital associative R -algebra whose dimension is finite. We consider the right modules of finite R -dimension

and denote \otimes_R by \otimes . For all $f, g \in Z_2^n$, a self-inverse R -linear isomorphism $g \rightarrow g^*$ such that $(fg)^* = g^*f^*$ is an anti-involution on R -algebra Z_2^n .

Definition 2.1.[7] Let n be a non-negative integer. An ordered sequence $a = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_s)$ such that $\sum_j a_j = n$ is called a composition or tuple of non-negative integers of order n . If two compositions $a = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_s)$ and $b = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s)$ are such that $\sum_j a_j \geq \sum_j b_j$ for each $j = 1, 2, \dots, s$, then $a \supseteq b$. Also if $a_j > b_j$, then $a \triangleright b$. Thus for $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_s$, a composition of non-negative integers $a = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_s)$ represents a partition. In particular, when $n = 0$, there is only one partition $()$.

Definition 2.1. [3] Let R be commutative ring with unit 1 and $Z_2^n(x)$ be an associative, unital R -algebra. Let Λ be a finite set with partial order \leq and for each $\lambda \in \Lambda$, let $M(\lambda)$ be a finite right indexing set. Then for all $(s, t) \in M(\lambda) \times M(\lambda)$, there is an element $C_{s,t}^\lambda \in Z_2^n$ such that there is an injective map $(\lambda, s, t) \rightarrow C_{s,t}^\lambda$ and

$$C_{s,t}a = \sum_{p \in M(\lambda)} R(t, p)C_{s,p}^\lambda \dots\dots(1)$$

is a free R -basis for Z_2^n . The action of Z_2^n on the right cell module Δ^λ is

$$C_t a = \sum_{p \in M(\lambda)} R_a(t, p)C_p \dots\dots(2)$$

Definition 2.2. [7] The wreath product \vec{S}_n can be redefined as

$$\vec{S}_n = \{\alpha \in S_{2n} \mid \text{if } \alpha(r) = s \text{ then } \theta(r^*) = s^*\}$$

where for each $r \in (1, 2, \dots, 2n)$, r^* , is given by :

$$r^* = \begin{cases} r + n, & 1 \leq r \leq n \\ r - n, & n < r \leq 2n \end{cases}$$

2.3. Elements of \vec{S}_4 using signed Brauer diagrams: Basis of the natural permutations of \vec{S}_4 are identified with the set of all signed Brauer diagrams consisting $2n$ dots. There will be two rows each having n dots and there are n signed edges connecting pairs of dots taking one from each row. This can be illustrated with an example:

For $n = 4$ and $2n = 8$, the anti-involution element $(17)(53)(28)(64)$ of \vec{S}_4 is identified with the signed Brauer diagram

Let $\sigma, \alpha \in \vec{S}_n$ be any two anti-involution elements. The conjugate of these two anti-involution elements is again an anti-involution element of \vec{S}_n .

For example: for $n = 4, 2n = 8$, if $\sigma = (12)(56)(34)(78), \alpha = (14)(58)(23)(67)$ are two anti-involution elements of \vec{S}_4 then the conjugate $\sigma^\alpha = (13)(57)(24)(68)$ in \vec{S}_4 is again an anti-involution element. This can be well understood through the signed Brauer diagrams:

$$\sigma = \begin{array}{cccc} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \diagdown & \diagup & \diagdown & \diagup \\ & & & \\ \diagup & \diagdown & \diagup & \diagdown \\ 5 & 6 & 7 & 8 \end{array} = (1\ 2)(5\ 6)(3\ 4)(7\ 8)$$

$$\alpha = \begin{array}{cccc} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \diagdown & \diagup & \diagdown & \diagup \\ & & & \\ \diagup & \diagdown & \diagup & \diagdown \\ 5 & 6 & 7 & 8 \end{array} = (1\ 4)(5\ 8)(2\ 3)(6\ 7) \quad \sigma^\alpha = \begin{array}{cccc} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \diagdown & \diagup & \diagdown & \diagup \\ & & & \\ \diagup & \diagdown & \diagup & \diagdown \\ 5 & 6 & 7 & 8 \end{array} = (1\ 3)(5\ 7)(2\ 4)(6\ 8)$$

3. Cellular algebras of wreath product $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$:

Let Z_2^n be a finite dimensional unital associative R -algebra. Consider the R -vector space $Z_2^{\otimes n} \otimes RS_n$. A pure tensor $\alpha \otimes f_1 \otimes f_2 \otimes \dots \otimes f_n$ in this vector space be written as $(\alpha; f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n)$. Then a well defined multiplication is given by

$$(\alpha; f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n)(\beta; g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n) = (\alpha\beta; f_{1\beta^{-1}}g_1, f_{2\beta^{-1}}g_2, \dots, f_{n\beta^{-1}}g_n)$$

for $\alpha, \beta \in S_n$ and $f_i, g_i \in Z_2^n$. A pure tensor $(\alpha; f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n)$ in \vec{S}_n where $\alpha \in S_n$ and $f_i \in Z_2^n$, can be represented by using signed Brauer diagram.

For example: Take $n = 6$, Let $\alpha, \beta \in S_n$ such that

$$(\alpha; f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5, f_6) = (1, 3, 6, 10, 5, 8)(7, 9, 12, 4, 11, 2)$$

and

$$(\beta; g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4, g_5, g_6) = (1, 9, 4, 6, 7, 3, 10, 12)$$

are the elements of \vec{S}_n .

Then their product

$$\begin{aligned} & (\alpha; f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5, f_6)(\beta; g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4, g_5, g_6) \\ &= (\gamma; h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4, h_5, h_6) \\ &= (1, 10, 5, 8, 9, 7, 4, 11, 2, 3)(6, 12). \end{aligned}$$

is an element in \vec{S}_n .

The same is illustrated using signed Brauer diagram where the product is obtained by resolving the two connected edges and the resulting element is an element of \vec{S}_n given by

$$(\gamma; f_6g_1, f_2g_2, f_1g_3, f_3g_4, f_5g_5, f_4g_6) = (1, 10, 5, 8, 9, 7, 4, 11, 2, 3)(6, 12).$$

$$=(1, 3, 12, 4, 11, 2, 7, 9, 6, 10, 5, 8)$$

$$=(1, 6)(7, 12)(2, 3, 4, 11)(8, 9, 10, 5)$$

$$=(1, 4, 2, 12, 11, 3, 7, 10, 8, 6, 5, 9)$$

Anti-involution $*$ of \vec{S}_n is given by

$$(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n)^* = (\alpha^{-1}; f_{(1)\alpha}^*, \dots, f_{(n)\alpha}^*)$$

where $\alpha \in S_n$ and $f_1, \dots, f_n \in Z_2^n$. The mapping of anti-involution elements takes place through the diagram by replacing each element f_i with its image f_i^* under the anti-involution on Z_2^n , and then sliding each element f_i^* to the bottom of the row.

3.1. Construction of modules for \vec{S}_n : Let μ be the s -part composition of n , A_1, \dots, A_s be Z_2^n modules and for each $j = 1, \dots, s$ let B_j be kS_μ module. $\vec{S}_\mu = Z_2^n \wr S_\mu$ be the subalgebra of $\vec{S}_n = Z_2^n \wr S_n$ spanned by all elements $(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n)$ where $f_j \in Z_2^n$ and $\alpha \in S_\mu$. Then

$A_1^{\otimes \mu_1} \otimes \dots \otimes A_s^{\otimes \mu_s} \otimes B_1^{\otimes \dots} \otimes B_s$ is \vec{S}_μ -module through the action

$$(a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n \otimes b_1 \otimes \dots \otimes b_s)(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n) = a_{(1)\alpha^{-1}} f_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{(n)\alpha^{-1}} f_n \otimes b_1 \alpha_1 \otimes \dots \otimes b_s \alpha_s,$$

where each $\alpha_i \in S_{\mu_i}$, are such that whenever S_μ is identified naturally with $S_{\mu_1} \times \dots \times S_{\mu_s}$ and α is identified with $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_s)$.

Therefore by induction, from $\vec{S}_\mu = Z_2^n \wr S_\mu$ to $\vec{S}_n = Z_2^n \wr S_n$, we get a module isomorphic to

$$A_1^{\otimes \mu_1} \otimes \dots \otimes A_s^{\otimes \mu_s} \otimes B_1 \otimes \dots \otimes B_s \otimes kR_\mu,$$

where the basis of vector space kR_μ is R_μ which contains coset representations of minimal length. Let $\gamma, \delta \in R_\mu$, and $\theta, \alpha \in S_\mu$ such that $\gamma\alpha = \theta\delta$, then the action of \vec{S}_n on kR_μ is given by

$$(a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_s \otimes b_1 \otimes \dots \otimes b_s \otimes \delta)(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n) = a_{(1)\theta^{-1}} f_1 \delta \otimes \dots \otimes a_{(n)\theta^{-1}} f_n \delta \otimes b_1 \theta_1 \otimes \dots \otimes b_s \theta_s,$$

Let $\bar{A} = (A_1, \dots, A_s)$ and $\bar{B} = (B_1, \dots, B_s)$ be the tuples and the modules obtained be $\Theta^\mu(\bar{A}, \bar{B})$. A pure tensor $a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n \otimes b_1 \otimes \dots \otimes b_s \otimes \delta$ is taken as a pure tensor for $\delta \in R_\mu$. To obtain the signed Brauer diagram of this tensor, first label the edges in the lower row from left to right with the elements $a_{(1)\delta^{-1}}, \dots, a_{(n)\delta^{-1}}$, then link them to the first μ_1 edges on the top row and label the linked edges with b_1 . Similarly link the next μ_2 edges on the top row and label the linked edges as b_2 , and so on.

For example, take $n = 5, s = 2, \mu = (3, 2)$ and $\delta = (1, 5, 3, 4, 2)(6, 10, 8, 9, 7)$ of \vec{S}_5 , then the tensor

$$a_1 \otimes a_2 \otimes a_3 \otimes a_4 \otimes a_5 \otimes b_1 \otimes b_2 \otimes \delta$$

can be represented by the diagram

The elements of A_j are associated with the edges b_j and hence $\Theta^\mu(\bar{A}, \bar{B})$ can be identified with the k -vector space by diagram of some element in R_μ where we see that for each $j = 1, 2, \dots, s$, $(\mu_1 + \dots + \mu_{j-1} + 1)$ th to $(\mu_1 + \dots + \mu_j)$ th edges are connected so as to form a single block which is labelled by an element of B_j . For $\delta \in R_\mu$, b_1, \dots, b_s labels in the top row and u_1, \dots, u_n labels in bottom row and the permutation diagram is $\delta \in R_\mu$. This represents pure tensor $u_{(1)\delta} \otimes \dots \otimes u_{(n)\delta} \otimes b_1 \otimes \dots \otimes b_s \otimes \delta$. Set of these elements span $\Theta^\mu(\bar{A}, \bar{B})$ but not linearly independent. The diagram

represents the pure tensor

$$u_2 \otimes u_3 \otimes u_5 \otimes u_4 \otimes u_1 \otimes b_1 \otimes b_2 \otimes (1, 5, 3, 4, 2)(6, 10, 8, 9, 7)$$

Consider another element $((1, 3, 4, 2)(6, 8, 9, 7); f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5)$ of $\overrightarrow{S}_{10} = Z_2 \wr S_5$,

Action of element of \overrightarrow{S}_{10} on the element of $\Theta^\mu(\overline{A}, \overline{B})$ is calculated as in the diagram

After this action, the element of \overrightarrow{S}_{10} from this diagram is $(1, 5, 4)(6, 10, 9)(2, 3)$.

This element is the product of elements from S_μ and R_μ .

That is $(1, 5, 3, 4, 2)(6, 10, 8, 9, 7) = (1, 5, 4)(2, 3).(6, 10, 9)(7, 8)$ where $(1, 5, 4)(2, 3) \in S_\mu$ and $(6, 10, 9)(7, 8) \in R_\mu$.

Proposition 3.2. If A_1, \dots, A_s are Z_2^n -modules, and B_1, \dots, B_s are kS_μ -modules, then for any composition μ which is s part of n with a_k and b_k as generators of A_k and B_k , $\Theta^\mu(\overline{A}, \overline{B})$ is a cyclic \overrightarrow{S}_n -module. The signed Brauer diagram given by

generates $\Theta^\mu(\overline{A}, \overline{B})$.

Proof: Let us denote the diagram in the proposition D . For each $a \in S_\mu$, apply $(a; j, \dots, j)$ of \overrightarrow{S}_n to replace each element b_k in D with an arbitrary element of B_k . For some $\delta \in R_\mu$, apply $(\delta; j, \dots, j)$ to arrange the strings of the diagram D . Then replace each element a_k with an arbitrary element of A_k by applying an element $(e; f_1, \dots, f_n)$. These diagrams span $\Theta^\mu(\overline{A}, \overline{B})$. This completes the proof.

Let Δ^λ be cell module of the cellular algebra Z_2^n . Then for $\alpha \in S_n$,

$$\alpha_\lambda : C_{s,t}^\lambda + \overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda} \rightarrow C_s^\lambda \times (C_t^\lambda)^*$$

determines a $Z_2^n - Z_2^n$ bi-module isomorphism from $Z_2^{n\lambda}/\overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda}$ to $\delta^\lambda \otimes_R (\Delta^\lambda)^*$. For all $s, t, u, v \in M(\lambda)$, there exist R -valued bi-linear form $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ such that

$$C_{s,t}^\lambda C_{u,v}^\lambda \equiv \langle C_t^\lambda \cdot C_u^\lambda \rangle C_{s,v}^\lambda \pmod{\overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda}}.$$

This bi-linear form plays an essential role in theory of cellular algebra

Lemma 3.3. Z_2^n be a cellular algebra with cell datum $(\Lambda, M, C, *)$. Let $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and $d \in \Delta^\lambda$ be non-zero. Then $a \rightarrow a \otimes d^*$ is a Z_2^n -module isomorphism of Δ^λ onto $\Delta^\lambda \otimes d^* \subseteq \Delta^\lambda \otimes_R (\Delta^\lambda)^*$.

Proof. $(\Delta^\lambda)^*$ is a free module and hence torsion free. Thus as Z_2^n -modules,

$$\Delta^\lambda \cong \Delta^\lambda \otimes_R R d^* = \Delta^\lambda \otimes d^*.$$

hence $x \rightarrow x \otimes d^*$ is an isomorphism.

Definition 3.4.[8] A cellular algebra is said to be cyclic cellular if every cell module of Z_2^n is cyclic.

Lemma 3.5. If Z_2^n is a cellular algebra with cell datum $(\Lambda, M, C, *)$ then following are equivalent.

- (i) Z_2^n is cellular.
- (ii) For each $\lambda \in \Lambda$, there exists an element $a_\lambda \in Z_2^{n\lambda}$ such that
 - (a) $a_\lambda \equiv a_\lambda^* \pmod{\overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda}}$
 - (b) $Z_2^{n\lambda} = Z_2^n a_\lambda Z_2^n + \overline{Z}_2$
 - (c) $(Z_2^n a_\lambda + \overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda}) / \overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda} \cong \Delta^\lambda$, as Z_2 -modules.

Proof. Suppose that Z_2^n is cyclic cellular. For each $\lambda \in \Lambda$, let δ^λ be the generator of the cell module Δ^λ . Let $a_\lambda \in Z_2^{n\lambda}$ be any lifting of $\alpha_\lambda^{-1}(\delta^\lambda \otimes (\delta^\lambda)^*)$. Then $(\delta^\lambda \otimes (\delta^\lambda)^*)^* = (\delta^\lambda \otimes (\delta^\lambda)^*)$ implies 2(a) is true. $Z_2^n(\delta^\lambda \otimes (\delta^\lambda)^*)Z_2^n = (\Delta^\lambda \otimes_R (\Delta^\lambda)^*)$ implies 2(b) is true.

We obtain Z_2^n -module isomorphism $z a_\lambda + \overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda} \rightarrow z \delta^{\lambda \otimes (\delta^\lambda)^*}$, by restricting α_λ . By lemma 3.3., $x \otimes (\delta^\lambda)^* \rightarrow x$ is an Z_2^n -module isomorphism from $\Delta^\lambda \otimes (\delta^\lambda)^*$ onto Δ^λ . By composing these two isomorphisms we get $z a_\lambda + \overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda} \rightarrow z \delta^\lambda$ such that $(Z_2^n a_\lambda + \overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda}) / \overline{Z}_2^{n\lambda} \cong \Delta^\lambda$. This proves 2(c).

Conversely, if (2) holds, then in particular 2(c) implies that each cell module is cyclic. Hence Z_2^n is cellular.

4.The iterated inflation structure of $\overrightarrow{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$

As stated by Konig and Xi in [5], prove that Brauer algebra is cellular by exhibiting a structure called iterated inflation. Special cases can be found in the papers of Graham and Lehrer[1]. R.Green[3] has applied iterated inflations to show that the wreath product $A \wr S_n$ is cellular for any cellular algebra A by showing it as an iterated inflation of tensor products of group algebras of symmetric group.

Let Z_2 be a cellular algebra with cell datum $(\Lambda, M, C, *)$ where $*$ denotes the anti involution. Let $|\Lambda| = s$, and $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_s$ be the elements of Λ such that $\lambda_i > \lambda_j$ for all $i < j$. Thus the numbering is in compatible with partial ordering on Λ . Let Δ^λ be the right cell module for every $\lambda \in \Lambda$. We shall write the elements of cellular basis $C_{s,t}^\lambda$ as $C_{s,t}$. Then the basis of $\overrightarrow{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ consists the elements of the form $(\alpha; C_{s_1, t_1}, \dots, C_{s_n, t_n})$ for $\alpha \in S_n$ and C_{s_k, t_k} is some element in the basis of Z_2 . We shall denote this basis as P . The elements of P are represented by the diagrams

This can be represented as

Thus the elements P can be represented as

This diagram represents the element

$$((1, 3, 2, 5, 4)(6, 8, 7, 10, 9); C_{u_4v_1}, C_{u_3v_2}, C_{u_1v_3}, C_{u_5v_4}, C_{u_2v_5}) \in \vec{S}_5 = Z_2 \wr S_5.$$

where $u_l, v_m \in M(\lambda)$ for some $\lambda \in \Lambda$. For each $l \in \{1, \dots, s\}$, let μ_l be the number of elements u_l in $M(\lambda)$ such that there exists a composition $\mu = \mu_1, \dots, \mu_s$ of n for any such diagram. We call it *layer index* of the diagram and also the element which it represents in P . Let kP be the k -span of all elements of P with layer index μ , and $I(n, s)$ be the set of all s -part composition of n with non-negative integer entries. Thus $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n = \bigoplus_{\mu \in I(n, s)} kP_\mu$. For layer index μ , the tuple (u_1, \dots, u_n) of n elements of $\sqcup_{\lambda \in \Lambda} M(\lambda)$ denotes the half diagram such that it has exactly μ_k elements of $M(\lambda_k)$ for each k . Let U_μ be the set of all half diagram of type μ . Then there exists a unique element $\epsilon \in R_\mu$ such that $(u_{(1)\epsilon}, \dots, u_{(n)\epsilon})$ lies in the set $M(\lambda_1)^{\mu_1} \times \dots \times M(\lambda_s)^{\mu_s}$. We call this ϵ the *shape* of the half diagram (u_1, \dots, u_n) .

Let $\alpha \in S_n$ be a permutation such that u_k is connected to $v_{(k)\alpha}$. Then there is an element

$$(\alpha; C_{u_{(1)\alpha^{-1}v_1}, \dots, C_{u_{(n)\alpha^{-1}v_n}}$$

in \vec{S}_n which has a layer index μ . This element can be split into three parts namely the half diagrams (u_1, \dots, u_n) of top rows and (v_1, \dots, v_n) of bottom rows of type μ and the element $(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_s)$ of the group $S_{\mu_1} \times \dots \times S_{\mu_s}$ where $\mu_k \in S_{\mu_k}$. This β_k records how the elements of $M(\lambda_k)$ on the top row is connected to the elements of $M(\lambda_k)$ in the bottom row. If ϵ, δ are the shapes of (u_1, \dots, u_n) and (v_1, \dots, v_n) respectively and β is the image of $(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_s)$ under the natural identification of $S_{\mu_1} \times \dots \times S_{\mu_s}$ with Young subgroup S_μ of S_n . Then $\beta = \epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta$. We now take B_μ to be the k -vector space with basis b_μ . Then the above decomposition has a k -linear bijection

$$B_\mu \otimes kS_\mu \otimes B_\mu \rightarrow kZ_2^n - \mu$$

given by the mapping

$$(u_1, \dots, u_n) \otimes \beta \otimes (v_1, \dots, v_n),$$

to

$$(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta; C_{u_{(1)\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta v_1}, \dots, C_{u_{(n)\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta v_n}}$$

where ϵ is the shape of (u_1, \dots, u_n) and δ is the shape of (v_1, \dots, v_n) . Thus we have a decomposition $\vec{S}_n = \bigoplus_{\mu \in I(n, s)} B_\mu \otimes kS_\mu \otimes B_\mu$, and this decomposition will allow us to exhibit the desired iterated inflation structure.

Now, we need ordering of $I(n, s)$. If (μ_1, \dots, μ_s) and $(\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_s)$ are elements of $I(n, s)$, then define $\mu \succeq_\Lambda \gamma$ such that

$$\sum \mu_k \geq \sum \gamma_k$$

where $\lambda_k \geq \lambda_l$ for each k . This is called the partial Λ -dominance order.

Lemma.4.1. Suppose that we have $a_1, \dots, a_s, b_1, \dots, b_s \in \{1, \dots, s\}$ such that $\lambda_{a_i} \geq \lambda_{b_i}$ for each i in the poset Λ and let $\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_s)$ and $\gamma = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_s)$ so that $\mu, \gamma \in I_{(n,s)}$. Then $\mu \succeq_{\Lambda} \gamma$ and if one of the inequalities $\lambda_{a_i} \geq \lambda_{b_i}$ is strict, then $\mu \triangleright_{\Lambda} \gamma$.

Proof: For each k , $\lambda_k \geq \lambda_l$ implies

$$\sum \mu_k \geq \sum \gamma_k$$

where

$$\sum \mu_k = |\{i : \lambda_{a_i} \geq \lambda_l\}|,$$

$$\sum \gamma_k = |\{i : \lambda_{b_i} \geq \lambda_l\}|.$$

But

$$\{i : \lambda_{a_i} \geq \lambda_l\} \subset \{i : \lambda_{b_i} \geq \lambda_l\} \text{ for } \lambda_{a_i} \geq \lambda_{b_i}.$$

Thus if there is one strict inequality $\lambda_{a_i} > \lambda_{b_i}$, then we get $\mu \neq \gamma$ and hence $\mu \triangleright_{\Lambda} \gamma$.

Proposition 4.2. Let $\mu \in I_{(n,s)}$, and $u = (u_1, \dots, u_n), v = (v_1, \dots, v_n) \in B_{\mu}$. Let $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_s \in S_{\mu}$ be such that the element of basis of Z_2 corresponding to the pure tensor $u \otimes \beta \otimes v$ has a layer index μ . Also, let $f = (\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n)$ be a pure tensor in $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$. Then $(u \otimes \beta \otimes v) \cdot f \cong u \otimes \beta \phi_{\mu}(v, f) \otimes \psi_{\mu}(v, f)$ modulo elements of basis of Z_2 whose layer index is strictly less than μ , where $\phi_{\mu}(v, f) \in S_{\mu}$ and $\psi_{\mu}(v, f) \in B_{\mu}$ are independent of u and β .

Proof. Let $\epsilon, \delta \in B_{\mu}$ be the shapes of u and v respectively, so that $u \otimes \beta \otimes v$ corresponds to the element

$$(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta; C_{u_{(1)}\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta, v_1}, \dots, C_{u_{(n)}\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta, v_n}).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & (u \otimes \beta \otimes v)(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n) \\ &= (\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta; C_{[u_{(1)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta)^{-1}, v_1]}, \dots, C_{[u_{(n)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta)^{-1}, v_n]}) \\ &= (\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha; C_{[u_{(1)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, v_1]f_1}, \dots, C_{[u_{(n)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, v_n]f_n}). \end{aligned}$$

For $k = 1, \dots, n$, let $s_k \in \{1, \dots, s\}$ be such that $u_{(k)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, v_{(k)\alpha^{-1}} \in M(\lambda_{s_k})$. Then from (1),

$$C_{[u_{(k)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, v_{(k)\alpha^{-1}}]f_k} \equiv \sum_{p \in M(\lambda)} R_{f_k}(v_{(k)\alpha^{-1}}, p_k) C_{[u_{(k)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, p_k]}$$

modulo cellular basis elements of lower cell index. Using this we get

$$\begin{aligned} & (u \otimes \beta \otimes v)(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n) \equiv \\ & \sum_{p_1} \cdots \sum_{p_n} (\prod_{k=1}^n R_{f_k}(v_{(k)\alpha^{-1}}, p_k)) (\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha; C_{[u_{(1)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, p_1]}, \dots, C_{[u_{(n)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, p_n]}) \dots (*) \end{aligned}$$

modulo elements of the basis of Z_2 of the form

$$(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha; C_{s_1, t_1}^{\lambda_{t_1}}, \dots, C_{s_n, t_n}^{\lambda_{t_n}}) \dots (**)$$

where for each k $\lambda_{s_k} \geq \lambda_{t_k}$ and for atleast one k the the inequality is strict. Let $\gamma = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_s)$ be the layer index of $(**)$. By lemma 4.1. we have $\mu \triangleright_{\Lambda} \gamma$, so that $(u \otimes \beta \otimes v)(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n)$ is congruent $(*)$ modulo elements of lower layer index.

Now, p_k lies in the same set $M(\lambda_{s_k})$ as $v_{(k)\alpha^{-1}}$, and from this we see that the shape of (p_1, \dots, p_n) is the unique element ψ of B_{μ} such that $\delta\alpha = \phi\psi$ for $\phi \in S_{\mu}$. Thus in $(*)$ we have

$$(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha; C_{[u_{(1)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, p_1]}, \dots, C_{[u_{(n)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\delta\alpha)^{-1}, p_n]}) \\ = (\epsilon^{-1}\beta\phi\psi; C_{[u_{(1)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\phi\psi)^{-1}, p_1]}, \dots, C_{[u_{(n)}(\epsilon^{-1}\beta\phi\psi)^{-1}, p_n]}).$$

which corresponds to the pure tensor $u \otimes \beta\phi \otimes (p_1, \dots, p_n)$ and hence $(*)$ is equal to

$$u \otimes \beta\phi \otimes (\sum_{p_1} \cdots \sum_{p_n} (\prod_{k=1}^n R_{f_k}(v_{(k)\alpha^{-1}}, p_k))(p_1, \dots, p_n)).$$

Thus, by setting $\phi_{\mu}(v, f)$ to be the unique element ϕ of S_{μ} so that $\delta\alpha = \phi\psi$ for $\psi \in B_{\mu}$ and $\psi_{\mu}(v, f)$ to be

$$(\prod_{k=1}^n R_{f_k}(v_{(k)\alpha^{-1}}, p_k))(p_1, \dots, p_n).$$

Further we observe that $(u \otimes \beta \otimes v)(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n) \equiv u \otimes \beta\phi_{\mu}(v, f) \otimes \psi_{\mu}(v, f)$ modulo lower layers whose values depend only on v and f as required. \square

Theorem 4.3. Let Z_2 be the cellular algebra with anti involution $*$ and poset Λ of cell indices. Let B_n^s be the set of all multi partitions of n of length s with the partial order : if $(a_1, \dots, a_s), (b_1, \dots, b_s) \in B_n^s$, then $(a_1, \dots, a_s) \geq (b_1, \dots, b_s)$ implies $(|a_1|, \dots, |a_s|) \geq_{\Lambda} (|b_1|, \dots, |b_s|)$ or that $|a_k| = |b_k|$ and $a_k \leq b_k$ for each k . Then $\overrightarrow{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is a cellular algebra for $\alpha \in S_n$ and $f_1, \dots, f_n \in Z_2^n$ by

$$(\alpha; f_1, \dots, f_n)^* = (\alpha^{-1}; f_{(1)\alpha}^*, \dots, f_{(n)\alpha}^*).$$

5. The cell modules and simple modules of the wreath product \overrightarrow{S}_n .

We know that cell modules $\Delta\lambda_j$ are indexed by the cell indices $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_s$. These are indexed by length s multipartitions of n . Let η_1, \dots, η_s be such a multipartition and μ the composition $(|\eta_1|, \dots, |\eta_s|)$, such that $\mu_j = \eta_j$.

$\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ as a k - vector space may be identified with

$$S^{\eta_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes S^{\eta_s} \otimes V_{\mu},$$

Let $(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n) \in \Lambda$ such that

$$(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n) = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_1(\mu_1 \text{ times}), \dots, \lambda_s, \dots, \lambda_s(\mu_s \text{ times}))$$

Let (X_1, \dots, X_n) be half diagram in B_{μ} . Then its shape is the unique element $\delta \in R_{\mu}$ such that it lies in $M(\theta_1\delta^{-1}) \times \cdots \times M(\theta_n\delta^{-1})$. Hence

$$B_{\mu} = \sqcup_{\delta \in B_{\mu}} M(\theta_1\delta^{-1}) \times \cdots \times M(\theta_n\delta^{-1}).$$

Therefore the half diagram (X_1, \dots, X_n) is identified with the pure tensor $C_{X_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes C_{X_n}$. and obtain the natural identification of k -vector spaces

$$V_{\mu} = \bigoplus_{\delta \in B_{\mu}} \Delta^{(\theta_1\delta^{-1})} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Delta^{(\theta_n\delta^{-1})}.$$

Further for $x_j \in S^{\eta_j}$ and $u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n$ is a pure tensor in V_{μ} the pure tensor of $\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ is

$$a_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes a_s \otimes u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n,$$

Then for $\phi_{\mu}(v, f) \in S_{\mu}$ it may be verified that the map taking the pure tensor

$$v_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes v_n \otimes b_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes b_s \otimes \theta$$

in $\Theta^\mu((\Delta^{\lambda_1}, \dots, \Delta^{\lambda_s}), (S^{\eta_1}, \dots, S^{\eta_s}))$ where $\theta \in R_\mu$ to the pure tensor

$$b_1 \cdots \otimes b_s \otimes v_{(1)\theta^{-1}} \otimes \cdots \otimes v_{(n)\theta^{-1}}$$

in $\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ is an isomorphism of $\overrightarrow{S_n}$ -modules. Thus by [3] we have the following remark,

Remark 5.1 The cell module $\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ is isomorphic to the module $\Theta^\mu((\Delta^{\lambda_1}, \dots, \Delta^{\lambda_s}), (S^{\eta_1}, \dots, S^{\eta_s}))$

Proposition 5.2. Let n_1, \dots, n_s be non-negative integers. Let $B_{n_1} \times \dots \times B_{n_s}$ be the poset of cell indices with the order $\lambda_i \geq \mu_i$ for all i . Then the group algebra $k(S_{n_1} \times \dots \times S_{n_s})$ is a cellular algebra with respect to the mapping $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_s) \rightarrow (\alpha_1^{-1}, \dots, \alpha_s^{-1})$ for all $\alpha_i \in S_{n_i}$ and cell module associated to $(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_s)$ is $S^{\lambda_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes S^{\lambda_s}$ with the action

$$(x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_s).(x_1\alpha_1) \otimes \cdots \otimes (x_s\alpha_s) \text{ for } x_i \in S^\lambda \text{ and } \alpha_i \in S_{n_i}.$$

The cell form is given on pure tensor by

$$\langle x_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes x_s, y_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes y_s \rangle = \langle x_1, y_1 \rangle \cdots \langle x_s, y_s \rangle$$

where each bilinear form on the right hand side is the appropriate cell form of S^{λ_i} .

Proposition 5.3. From [3] we have that if Z_2 is a k -algebra with anti involution $*$, then

$$Z_2^n \cong \bigoplus_{\mu \in I} V_\mu \otimes B_\mu \otimes V_\mu$$

of Z_2^n where I is the partially ordered set, each V_μ is a k -vector space and each B_μ is cellular algebra over k with respect to cell datum $(\Lambda_\mu, M_\mu, C, *)$. Hence Z_2^n can be identified with this direct sum of tensor products and $V_\mu \otimes B_\mu \otimes V_\mu$ as the μ -th layer of Z_2^n . Also for each $\mu \in I$ there is unique B_μ -valued k -bilinear form ϕ_μ on V_μ such that for any $u, v, x, y \in V_\mu$ and $b, c \in B_\mu$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_\mu(y, u) &= \phi_\mu(u, y)^* \text{ and} \\ (x \otimes c \otimes y)(u \otimes b \otimes v) &\equiv x \otimes c\phi_\mu(y, u)b \otimes v \text{ mod } H(< \mu). \end{aligned}$$

where $H(< \mu) = \bigoplus_{\gamma < \mu} V_\gamma \otimes B_\gamma \otimes V_\gamma$

Further, for $(\mu, \lambda) \in \Lambda$, let $\Delta^{(\mu, \lambda)}$ denoted as Δ^λ be the right cell module of Z_2 so that for any $x, y \in V_\mu$ and $z, w \in \Delta^\lambda$, we have

$$\langle z \otimes x, w \otimes y \rangle = \langle z, w\phi_\mu(y, x) \rangle_\lambda$$

as the cell form.

Proposition 5.4. The wreath product $\overrightarrow{S_n} = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is cyclic cellular if Z_2^n is cyclic cellular.

Proof. By Proposition 5.2., we understand that the multiplication within each layer of $\overrightarrow{S_n} = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is determined by a bilinear form ϕ_μ . Let $(u_1, \dots, u_n), (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be the half diagram in V_μ , so that $u = C_{u_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes C_{u_n}$ and $v = C_{v_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes C_{v_n}$ are pure tensors in V_μ . Then

$$(u \otimes e \otimes u)(v \otimes e \otimes v) \equiv u\phi_\mu(u, v) \otimes v \dots (**)$$

modulo lower layers. The element $(u \otimes e \otimes u)$ of $\overrightarrow{S_n} = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is represented by the diagram

Exactly the similar way can represent the element $v \otimes e \otimes v$ by a diagram. The product $(u \otimes e \otimes u)(v \otimes e \otimes v)$ will now be represented as

..(****)

For $i = 1, \dots, n$, and $u_i \in M(\lambda_{s_i})$, we can expand the products $C_{u_i, u_i} C_{v_i, v_i}$ in terms of the linear combination of cellular basis elements $C_{X, Y}^{\lambda_{t_i}}$ where $\lambda_{t_i} \leq \lambda_{s_i}$ we get the diagram of the form

By Lemma 4.1. it follows that all such diagrams have layer index utmost μ and the element v_i do not lie in $M(\lambda_{s_i})$ implies that all the diagrams in the expansion have layer index strictly less than μ . Also in by (**), in such a case we see that $\phi_\mu(u, v) = 0$. Suppose that for each i , v_i lies in $M(\lambda_{s_i})$, then as stated in [3], since

$$C_{u_i, u_i} C_{v_i, v_i} \equiv \langle C_{u_i}, C_{v_i} \rangle C_{u_i, v_i}$$

modulo cellular basis elements of lower index, where $\langle . \rangle$ is the suitable cell form. By lemma 4.1. (****) is congruent modulo lower layers to

representing the element $\langle C_{u_1}, C_{v_1} \rangle \cdots \langle C_{u_n}, C_{v_n} \rangle (u \otimes e \otimes v)$. Therefore in this case

$$\phi(u, v) = \langle C_{u_1}, C_{v_1} \rangle \cdots \langle C_{u_n}, C_{v_n} \rangle.$$

From proposition 5.2., if for $z, w \in \Delta^\lambda$, $z_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes z_s \otimes u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n$ and $w_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes w_s \otimes v_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes v_n$ are pure tensors in the cell module $\Delta^{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s}$ then

$$\langle z_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes z_s \otimes u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n, w_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes w_s \otimes v_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes v_n \rangle = \langle z_1, u_1 \rangle \cdots \langle z_s, u_s \rangle \langle w_1, v_1 \rangle \cdots \langle w_s, v_s \rangle$$

If u_i and v_i lie in the same Δ^λ , for each $i = 1, \dots, n$,

$$\langle z_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes z_s \otimes u_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes u_n, w_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes w_s \otimes v_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes v_n \rangle = 0$$

otherwise.

By remark 5.1.,

$$\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)} \cong S^{\eta_1} \otimes \dots \otimes S^{\eta_s} \otimes V_\mu \cong \bigoplus_{\theta \in R_\mu} S^{\eta_1} \otimes \dots \otimes S^{\eta_s} \otimes \Delta^{(\theta_1 \delta^{-1})} \otimes \Delta^{(\theta_n \delta^{-1})}$$

For $\theta \in R_\mu$ let $\Gamma_\theta = S^{\eta_1} \otimes \dots \otimes S^{\eta_s} \otimes \Delta^{(\theta_1 \delta^{-1})} \otimes \Delta^{(\theta_n \delta^{-1})}$. If θ, β be distinct elements of R_μ and $u \in \Gamma_\theta$ and $v \in \Gamma_\beta$ then $(u, v) = 0$. This implies that if R_θ is the radical restriction of Γ_θ of $\langle \cdot \rangle$, then the radical cell of $\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ is $\bigoplus_{\theta \in R_\mu} R_\theta$.

Thus we have the following results on the simple and cell modules $P^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ and semi-simplicity of $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$.

Theorem 5.4. The set $(\hat{B}_n^s)_0$ consists of exactly those set of elements $(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s) \in \hat{B}_n^s$ such that $\eta_j = ()$ whenever $\lambda_j \in \Lambda \Lambda_0$ so that the cell radical of $\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ is a proper submodule of $\Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ and $(\hat{B}_n^s)_0$ indexes the simple modules of $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$.

Theorem 5.5. If $(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s) \in (\hat{B}_n^s)_0$ then from proposition 4.3., there exists an isomorphism of k - vector spaces

$$P^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)} \cong Q^{\eta_1} \otimes \dots \otimes Q^{\eta_s} \otimes P^{\theta_1 \delta^{-1}} \otimes \dots \otimes P^{\theta_n \delta^{-1}}.$$

Theorem 5.6. If $(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s) \in (\hat{B}_n^s)_0$ then $P^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)} \cong \Delta^{(\eta_1, \dots, \eta_s)}$ if and only if $Q^{\eta_j} = S^{\eta_j}$ for $j = 1, \dots, s$ and whenever $\eta_j \neq ()$, $P^{\lambda_j} \cong \Delta^{\lambda_j}$.

Theorem 5.7. [3] If Z_2 is a cellular algebra, then $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is semisimple if and only if both Z_2 and kS_n are semisimple.

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